

Fisher Information, Minimization and the Schrodinger Equation

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In classical mechanics, it is often argued that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by maximizing entropy subject to a constraint. A historical derivation of this distribution from the Boltzmann transport equation, however, does not seem to make use of entropy extremization, but rather uses two particle scattering, equal probability for time reversal scattering and conservation of kinetic energy. I.e. use is made of $F(p_1)F(p_2)=F(p_3)F(p_4)$ ((1)) where $F(p)$ is the probability distribution for momentum p . Furthermore, the Boltzmann transport equation is not necessary for obtaining ((1)), it follows from an “and” condition of probability, independence and time reversal ideas. Recently, there have been a number of papers in the literature describing how the extremization of Fisher information subject to a constraint may lead to the derivation of the Schrodinger equation. The constraint appears to be related to the potential energy. This, however, begs the question: Why does one need a constraint on potential energy and not use some other constraint? The potential energy $V(x)$ is a function of x so $F(x)V(x)$ provides geometric information about $F(x)$, the spatial probability. If geometric information is the only consideration, it seems any function of x could provide similar information; there would be no reason to choose $V(x)$ over others. Thus, it seems the idea of potential energy or energy in general is of fundamental importance. In this note, we examine conditions used in one source in the literature to extremize Fisher information to obtain the time-independent Schrodinger equation and then consider this process in relation to the ground state of the oscillator which mimics classical statistical mechanics. We find that in such a case, no extremization is necessary and that the integral being maximized equals the constraint. For cases other than the oscillator ground state, however, the Fisher information extremization seems interesting except for the fact that an integral: $\int dx V(x) F(x)$ seems to be forced into the problem. We try to argue that one may formulate that Schrodinger equation in terms of a plane wave average for kinetic energy which together with conservation of total energy at each point x yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation. In this equation, $W(x)$, the wavefunction, appears as a normalization constant. This equation appears as an operator $B(x)W(x) = EW(x)$ which we argue is of the form of the result of an extremization equation. Thus, given the Schrodinger equation, one may find a function, which when minimized or maximized yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation. That does not necessarily mean one must use extremization in order to obtain the equation, although it should give some insight into the problem.

Results of Extremization of Fisher Information

In (1), a very detailed set of rules is presented to obtain the following extremization function:

$$\int dx \frac{1}{p(x)} \left[\frac{d}{dx} p(x) \right]^2 + b \int dx p(x) C(x) \quad ((2))$$

Here $p(x)$ is a spatial probability distribution, $C(x)$ is a constraint function and b a Lagrange multiplier. Extremizing ((2)) with $p(x)=W(x)W(x)$ seems to yield:

$$-8 \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + 2b C(x) W(x) = 0 \quad ((3))$$

(In (1), the factors of 8 and 2 do not appear, but the form is the same.)

It is suggested that ((3)) becomes the time independent Schrodinger equation if $C(x)$ is chosen to be proportional to $E-V(x)$.

Case of the Ground State of a Harmonic Oscillator

Given ((3)), consider the case of the ground state harmonic oscillator for which $W(x)=B\exp(-ax^2)$ where B is a constant. Then $p(x)=BB \exp(-2ax^2)$. It is interesting to note that for this case:

$$\frac{d}{dx} p(x) = D(x) p(x) \quad ((4))$$

If this is the case, the function containing Fisher's information being maximized in ((2)) is of the identical form as the constraint i.e.

$$\int dx \frac{1}{p(x)} \left[\frac{d}{dx} p(x) \right]^2 = \int dx D(x)D(x) p(x) dx. \quad ((5))$$

Thus, if $D(x)D(x)=C(x)$ the constraint and the function to be minimized are the same, and no minimization occurs. (It will be shown that this is also the case for all classical statistical mechanical problems with a potential.)

In other words, for a specific example no minimization occurs, so it seems that some principle must be at work.

It should be noted, however, that ((4)) holds in quantum mechanics only for the oscillator ground state, so almost all problems satisfy the minimized Fisher condition. As argued in the introduction, however, it seems that the choice of $C(x)$ as proportional to $E-V(x)$ as a constraint is arbitrary. There must be a reason to choose this constraint instead of others and it seems that some "general principle" possibly not related to information theory is behind that choice. On the other hand, information theory might be related to kinetic energy or potential energy.

It should also be noted that for the oscillator ground state, $\int dx \frac{1}{p(x)} \left[\frac{d}{dx} p(x) \right]^2$ is proportional to Shannon's entropy $\int dx p(x) \ln(p(x))$ which is not normally the case in quantum mechanics. Thus, one could try to argue that for the oscillator ground state, Shannon's entropy is being extremized.

The Time-Independent Schrodinger Equation as the Result of a Minimization

Consider formulating the Schrodinger equation in the following manner.

1. Assume there is a strange type of quantum particle (not a point particle) with internal motion modeled by $\exp(ipx)$ (actually $\exp(ipx-iEt)$).
2. Assume such a particle is scattered from one p to another in a potential.
3. Assume an average kinetic energy exists at any point x .
4. Assume there is conservation of energy at each point x .

Then:

$$\left[\sum_{\text{over } p} \frac{p^2}{2m} \exp(ipx) \right] / W(x) + V(x) = E \quad ((5.5))$$

Here $W(x)$ is a normalization constant = $\sum_{\text{over } p} \exp(ipx)$, i.e. the wavefunction. ((5.5)) can be rewritten as: $(-1/2m) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx} W(x) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x)$ ((5.6))

Now ((5.6)) has the form of an operator $B(x)$ which upon acting on $W(x)$ yields the same functional form $W(x)$ times a constant. In linear algebra, this is an eigenvalue equation. It seems, however, that ((5.6)) can also be thought of as the result of an extremization problem. Consider a function $J(W(x))$. Imagine changing $W(x)$ to $W(x) + dW(x)$, where $dW(x)$ is a different functional form. If one can find an equation for $dW(x)$ which leads to a change in J , one can obtain the functional form of $dW(x)$. If it is proportional to $W(x)$, then there is really no change in $W(x)$ except for scaling and so $W(x)$ is a kind of extremum in the problem. Thus, it seems that the time-independent Schrodinger equation, as an eigenvalue problem, can be related to the idea of extremization, but that it is not necessary to do so.

Fisher Information and Kinetic and Potential Energy

It seems the idea of Fisher information may be useful in determining ideas about the nature of kinetic and potential energy. It is seen from ((3)) that Fisher's information is related to kinetic energy and the constraint to potential. In the case of classical statistical mechanics, $\ln(F(p)) = p^2/2m$. $\ln(F(p))$ is often called a lack of information, thus $p^2/2m$ must also be a lack of information. If one considers p^2 geometrically, it is proportional to the area of a sphere of radius p . Thus, a p vector's end spans this sphere. This might perhaps be thought of as a geometric lack of information. The bigger the surface area, the greater the uncertainty. (This idea would have to be modified a little for special relativity.)

Classical Statistical Mechanics

The Maxwell-Boltzmann momentum distribution is often derived by maximizing entropy subject to a constraint on energy. This leads to $F(p)=C \exp(-p^2/2mT)$. This result, however, can be obtained with no notion of extremization or entropy. Namely, one may argue that two particle elastic scattering occurs. The “and” condition of probability states the probability of having two independent particles collide at point x is $F(p_1)F(p_2)$. This will produce particles moving with momenta p_3 and p_4 , subject to conservation of momentum, after the collision. If the overall probability of the time reversed collision $F(p_3)F(p_4)$ is the same, then it seems that $F(p)$ will not change in time. (This is similar to the rate of a breakup equalling the rate of synthesis.) Thus:

$$F(p_1)F(p_2) = F(p_3)F(p_4) \quad \text{or} \quad \ln(F(p_1)) + \ln(F(p_2)) = \ln(F(p_3)) + \ln(F(p_4)) \quad ((6))$$

Equation ((6)) is of the form of conservation law. There is another conservation law in the problem, namely:

$$p_1^2/2m + p_2^2/2m = p_3^2/2m + p_4^2/2m \quad ((7))$$

A solution is set: $\ln [F(p)] = -C p^2/2m$ ((8)) and this is the Maxwell-Boltzmann solution. One may try to enforce a stronger statement by suggesting that ((7)) is the only physical conservation statement (which does not depend on the sign of p) in the problem (momentum conservation does), thus the conservation statement ((6)) must equal ((7)). In a sense, a fundamental law of physics for elastic scattering ((7)) has placed a constraint on a statistical picture ((6)). This would be interesting because it would suggest that $p^2/2m$ is related to a lack of information.

For the case of a potential $V(x)$, one notes that $p^2/2m$ at x is equal to $p^2/2m + V(x)$ at another point x . Thus, one can use: $F(p,x) = \exp(-p^2/2mT - V(x)/T)$. Thus, spatial density also does not need to follow from maximization of entropy. It should be noted that for all cases of $V(x)$ in classical statistical mechanics:

$$d/dx p(x) = (-1/T) p(x) d/dx V(x)$$

Thus, the function with Fisher’s information to be extremized in ((3))

$$\text{Integral } dx \, 1/p(x) [d/dx p(x)]^2 \quad \text{is always equal to} \quad \text{Integral } dx \, p(x) (1/T^2) [d/dx V(x)]^2$$

This, however, is of the form of the constraint equation $\text{Integral } dx \, C(x) p(x)$ with $C(x) = (1/T^2) [d/dx V(x)]^2$ so no maximization is occurring in classical statistical mechanics.

Note that for the case of the oscillator, but not other cases, $\text{Integral } dx \, 1/p(x) [d/dx p(x)]^2$ is proportional to Shannon’s entropy.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems maximization of Fisher information subject to constraints is being used frequently in the literature. We argue that such maximization does not occur for classical statistical mechanics or the ground state quantum oscillator. The idea may, however, be useful for all of the other cases of quantum mechanics, We have argued, however, that conservation of energy seems to be key. We also argue that the constraint used in Fisher information extremization, related to $V(x)$, seems forced. Perhaps a lack of information may be linked to kinetic and potential energy. We note, however, that the idea of a lack of information may be important in physics. For example, we note that for the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution $\ln(F(p)) = p^*p/2m$. p^*p is proportional to the area of a sphere and so the bigger the sphere the greater the lack of information, i.e. one knows less and less which point on the sphere the p vector touches.

Reference

Dimitrov, Vesselin, On Shannon-Jaynes Entropy and Fisher Information
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